

CUBIC IDEALS OF PO- Γ -SEMIGROUPS

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Abstract:

In this paper, we introduce the concept of cubic ideals of po- Γ -semigroups, which is generalized concept of fuzzy ideals of po- Γ -semigroups in order to obtain some characterization theorems. Operator po-semigroups of a po- Γ -semigroup have been made to work by obtaining various relationships between cubic ideals of a po- Γ -semigroup and that of its operator semigroups. We also investigated some of its properties with examples.

Key Words: Semigroup, Γ -Semigroup, po- Γ -Semigroup, Ideal, Bi-Ideal, Interior Ideal, Cubic Ideal, Cubic Bi-Ideal, Cubic Interior Ideal, Left Operator & Right Operator.

1. Introduction:

The important concept of fuzzy set has been introduced by Lofti.A. Zadeh [25]. Since then the work on fuzzy sets appeared showing its importance in various branches of mathematics. In 1971 Rosenfeld [18] introduced the concept of fuzzy group. R. Biswas [1] introduced the notion of fuzzy subgroup and antifuzzy subgroups. Semigroup is an algebraic structure consisting of a non-empty set S together with an associative binary operation. The formal study of semigroups began in the early 20th century. Kuroki [12, 13, 14] characterized several class of semigroups in terms of fuzzy left ideals, fuzzy right ideals, fuzzy bi-ideals. In [23, 24] X.Y. Xie introduced the ideal extensions of fuzzy ideals in semigroups. The idea of fuzzy bi-ideals in semigroups has been introduced by W.J. Lie [16]. In 1984 the notion of Γ -semigroups was introduced by M.K. Sen [20]. In 1986 M.K. Sen and N.K. Saha [21] modified the definition of sen's Γ -semigroup. This newly defined Γ -semigroup is known as one sided Γ -semigroup. Γ -semigroup has been analyzed by a lot of mathematicians, for instance by Chattopadhyay [2], T.K. Dutta and N.C. Adhikari [6, 7, 8]. They defined different properties of po- Γ -semigroup by defining operator po-semigroups of such type of po- Γ -semigroups. In 1996 Y.I. Kwon and S.K. Lee [15] introduced po- Γ -semigroups (partially ordered Γ -semigroups). Jun et al. [10] introduced the new concept called cubic sets. These structures encompass interval-valued fuzzy set and fuzzy set. Also Jun et al. [9] introduced the notion of cubic subgroups. V. Chinnadurai et al. [4] introduced cubic ideals of Γ -semigroups. The purpose of this paper to introduce the notion of cubic ideals of po- Γ -semigroups. We investigate some basic results, examples and properties.

2. Preliminaries:

Now we recall some known concepts related to cubic ideals of po- Γ -semigroups from the literature, which will be needed in the sequel.

Definition 2.1: [5] Let S and Γ be two non-empty sets. Then S is called a Γ -semigroup if there exist a mapping from $S \times \Gamma \times S \rightarrow S$ written as $(a, \alpha, b) \rightarrow a\alpha b$ satisfying the identity $(a\alpha b)\beta c = a\alpha(b\beta c)$, for all $a, b, c \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.2: [3] Let S be a semigroup. By a subsemigroup of S , we mean a non-empty subset A of S such that $A^2 \subseteq A$.

Definition 2.3: [3] Let S be a Γ -semigroup. By Γ -subsemigroup, we mean a non-empty subset A of S such that if $A\Gamma A \subseteq A$.

Definition 2.4: [7] A Γ -semigroup S is called po- Γ -semigroup if for any $a, b, c \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$, $a \leq b$ implies $a\alpha c \leq b\alpha c$ and $c\alpha a \leq c\alpha b$.

Definition 2.5: [7] Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup. A non-empty subset A of S is said to be right (left) ideal of S if
i) $A\Gamma S \subseteq A$ ($S\Gamma A \subseteq A$)

ii) if $x \in A$ and $y \in S$, such that $y \leq x$ then $y \in A$.

Definition 2.6: [22] Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup. A Γ -subsemigroup A of S is said to be bi-ideal of S if
i) $A\Gamma S\Gamma A \subseteq A$

ii) if $x \in A$ and $y \in S$, such that $y \leq x$ then $y \in A$.

Definition 2.7: [17] Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup. A Γ -subsemigroup A of S is said to be interior ideal of S if
i) $S\Gamma A\Gamma S \subseteq A$

ii) if $x \in A$ and $y \in S$, such that $y \leq x$ then $y \in A$.

Definition 2.8: [5] A fuzzy subset μ of a po- Γ -semigroup S is called a fuzzy Γ - subsemigroup of S , if $\mu(xy\gamma) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$. $\forall x, y \in S$ and $\forall \gamma \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.9: [19] A fuzzy subset μ of a po- Γ -semigroup S is called a fuzzy right (left) ideal of S , if
i) $x \leq y \Rightarrow \mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$

ii) $\mu(x\alpha y) \geq \mu(x)$, $(\mu(x\alpha y) \geq \mu(y)) \forall x, y \in S$. and $\alpha \in \Gamma$. if μ is both a fuzzy left and a fuzzy right ideal of S , then μ is called a fuzzy ideal of S .

Definition 2.10: [22] A fuzzy Γ -subsemigroup μ of a po- Γ - semigroup S is called a fuzzy bi-ideal of S , if
 i) $x \leq y \Rightarrow \mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$

ii) $\mu(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(z)\} \forall x, y, z \in S$. and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.11: [17] A fuzzy Γ -subsemigroup μ of a po- Γ - semigroup S is called a fuzzy interior ideal of S , if
 i) $x \leq y \Rightarrow \mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$

ii) $\mu(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \mu(y) \forall x, y, z \in S$. and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.12: [3] An interval-valued fuzzy subset $\bar{\mu}$ of X is called a fuzzy left (right) ideal of X , if $\bar{\mu}(xy) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$, $(\bar{\mu}(xy) \geq \bar{\mu}(x))$, $\forall x, y \in X$. if $\bar{\mu}$ is both an interval-valued fuzzy left and right ideal of X , then $\bar{\mu}$ is called an interval-valued fuzzy ideal of X .

Definition 2.13: [7] Let S be a Γ - semigroup. Let us define a relation ρ on $S \times \Gamma$ as follows $(x, \alpha)\rho(y, \beta)$ if and only if $xas = y\beta s \forall s \in S$ and $\gamma x\alpha = \gamma y\beta \forall \gamma \in \Gamma$. The ρ is an equivalence relation. Let $[x, \alpha]$ denote the equivalence class containing (x, α) . Let $L = \{[x, \alpha] : x \in S, \alpha \in \Gamma\}$. Then L is a semigroup with respect to the multiplication defined by $[x, \alpha][y, \beta] = [x\alpha y, \beta]$. This semigroup L is called the left operator semigroup of the Γ -semigroup S . Dually the right operator semigroup R of Γ -semigroup S is defined where the multiplication is defined by $[a, \alpha][\beta, b] = [\alpha a\beta, b]$.

Let $((S, \Gamma), \leq)$ be a po- Γ - semigroup. We define a relation \leq on L by $[a, \alpha] \leq [b, \beta]$ if and only if $aas \leq b\beta s$ for all $s \in S$ and $\gamma a\alpha \leq \gamma b\beta$ for all $\gamma \in \Gamma$. With respect to this relation L becomes a po-semigroup. In a similar way R can be made into a po-semigroup.

If there exist an element $[e, \delta] \in L$ ($[\gamma, f] \in R$) such that $e\delta s = s$ (resp. $s\gamma f = s$) for all $s \in S$ then $[e, \delta]$ (resp. $[\gamma, f]$) is called the left (resp. right) unity of S .

Now let S be a Γ - semigroup with unities, L and R are po-semigroups. We define a relation \leq in S by $a \leq b$ if and only if $[a, \alpha] \leq [b, \alpha]$ in L and $[\alpha, a] \leq [\alpha, b]$ in R for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. We also define a relation \leq in Γ by $\alpha \leq \beta$ if and only if $[a, \alpha] \leq [a, \beta]$ in L and $[\alpha, a] \leq [\beta, a]$ in R for all $a \in S$. With respect these relations S becomes a po- Γ - semigroup.

Definition 2.14: [9] Let X be a non empty set. A cubic set \mathcal{A} is a structure of the form $\mathcal{A} = \{ \langle x, \bar{\mu}(x), \lambda(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ and denoted by $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}_A, \lambda \rangle$, $\bar{\mu}_A = [\mu_A^-, \mu_A^+]$ is an interval-valued fuzzy set (briefly, IVF) in X and $\lambda: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a fuzzy set in X .

Definition 2.15: [11] For any non-empty subset G of a set X , the characteristic cubic set of G is defined to be a structure $\chi_G(x) = \langle x, \bar{\mu}_{\chi_G}(x), \gamma_{\chi_G}(x) \rangle : x \in X$ which is briefly denoted by $\chi_G(x) = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_G}(x), \gamma_{\chi_G}(x) \rangle$.

Where $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_G}(x) = \begin{cases} [1,1] & \text{if } x \in G \\ [0,0] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$ and $\gamma_{\chi_G}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \in G \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Definition 2.16: [2] A mapping f from a Γ - semigroup P to another Γ - semigroup Q is called a homomorphism, if $f(x\gamma y) = f(x)\gamma f(y) \forall x, y \in S$ and $\forall \gamma \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.17: [9] Let X and Y be given classical sets. A mapping $f: X \rightarrow Y$ induces two mappings

$$C_f: C(X) \rightarrow C(Y), \mathcal{A}_1 \rightarrow C_f(\mathcal{A}_1) \text{ and } C_f^{-1}: C(Y) \rightarrow C(X), \mathcal{A}_2 \rightarrow C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}_2).$$

Where the mapping C_f is called cubic transformation and C_f^{-1} is called inverse cubic transformation.

Definition 2.18: [9] Let f be a mapping from a set X to Y and $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic set of X then the image of X $C_f(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f(\bar{\mu}), C_f(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic set of Y is defined by

$$C_f(\mathcal{A})(y) = \begin{cases} C_f(\bar{\mu})(y) = \begin{cases} \sup_{f(x)=y} \bar{\mu}(x) & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) \neq \emptyset \text{ for all } y \in Y \\ [0,0] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ C_f(\omega)(y) = \begin{cases} \inf_{f(x)=y} \omega(x) & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) \neq \emptyset \text{ for all } y \in Y \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

And

Let f be a mapping from a set X to Y and $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic set of Y then the pre image of Y $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic set of X is defined by

$$C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A})(x) = \begin{cases} C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x)) = \bar{\mu}(f(x)) & \text{for all } x \in X \\ C_f^{-1}(\omega(x)) = \omega(f(x)) & \text{for all } x \in X \end{cases}$$

3. Main Results:

In this section we introduced the notion of cubic ideals of po- Γ - semigroups and discuss some of its properties with examples.

Definition 3.1: A cubic subset $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ of a po- Γ - semigroup S is called a cubic right (left) ideal of S , if
 i) $x \leq y \Rightarrow \bar{\mu}(x) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x) \leq \omega(y)$

ii) $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y) \geq \bar{\mu}(x)$ and $\omega(x\alpha y) \leq \omega(x)$ ($\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x\alpha y) \leq \omega(y)$) $\forall x, y \in S$. and $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

if $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is both a cubic left and a cubic right ideal of S , then $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is called a cubic ideal of S .

Example 3.2: Let S be the set of all non-positive integers without zero and Γ be the set of all non-positive even

integers without zero. Then S is a Γ - semigroup where $x\alpha y$ denote the usual multiplication of integers x, α, y for all $x, y \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Then by routine calculation it is observed that S is a po- Γ - semigroup.

Define an interval-valued fuzzy set $\bar{\mu}: S \rightarrow D[0,1]$ by

$$\bar{\mu}(x) = \begin{cases} [0.1,0.2] & \text{if } x = -1 \\ [0.3,0.4] & \text{if } x = -2 \\ [0.5,0.6] & \text{if } x < -2 \end{cases}$$

Define a fuzzy set $\omega: S \rightarrow [0,1]$ by

$$\omega(x) = \begin{cases} 0.8 & \text{if } x = -1 \\ 0.4 & \text{if } x = -2 \\ 0.2 & \text{if } x < -2 \end{cases}$$

Hence $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic ideal of po- Γ -semigroup S .

Definition 3.3: A cubic subset $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ of a po- Γ -semigroup S is called a cubic Γ - subsemigroup of S , if

- i) $\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\}$
- ii) $\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\} \quad \forall x, y \in S \text{ and } \forall \gamma \in \Gamma$.

Definition 3.4: A cubic Γ -subsemigroup $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ of a po- Γ -semigroup S is called a cubic bi-ideal of S , if

- i) $x \leq y \Rightarrow \bar{\mu}(x) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x) \leq \omega(y)$
- ii) $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\}$ and $\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(z)\} \quad \forall x, y, z \in S \text{ and } \alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Definition 3.5: A cubic Γ -subsemigroup $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ of a po- Γ -semigroup S is called a cubic interior ideal of S , if

- i) $x \leq y \Rightarrow \bar{\mu}(x) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x) \leq \omega(y)$
- ii) $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \omega(y) \quad \forall x, y, z \in S \text{ and } \alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Definition 3.6: Let f be a mapping from a po- Γ -semigroup S to a po- Γ -semigroup S^1 and $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic set of S^1 then the pre image of S^1 $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic set of S is defined by

$$C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A})(x) = \begin{cases} C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x)) = \bar{\mu}(f(x)) & \text{for all } x \in S \\ C_f^{-1}(\omega(x)) = \omega(f(x)) & \text{for all } x \in S \end{cases}$$

Definition 3.7: Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup, L be the left operator and R be the right operator, then

For a cubic set (R) $\mathcal{A}_1 = \langle \bar{\mu}_1, \omega_1 \rangle$ we define a cubic set (S) $\mathcal{A}_1^* = \langle \bar{\mu}_1^*, \omega_1^* \rangle = \langle (\bar{\mu}_1)^*, (\omega_1)^* \rangle$ by

$$(\bar{\mu}_1)^*(x) = \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \bar{\mu}_1([\gamma, x]) \text{ and } (\omega_1)^*(x) = \sup_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \omega_1([\gamma, x]) \text{ where } x \in S.$$

For a cubic set (S) $\mathcal{A}_2 = \langle \bar{\mu}_2, \omega_2 \rangle$ we define a cubic set (R) $\mathcal{A}_2^{*1} = \langle \bar{\mu}_2^*, \omega_2^* \rangle = \langle (\bar{\mu}_2)^{*1}, (\omega_2)^{*1} \rangle$ by

$$(\bar{\mu}_2)^{*1}([\alpha, x]) = \inf_{s \in S} \bar{\mu}_2(s\alpha x) \text{ and } (\omega_2)^{*1}([\alpha, x]) = \sup_{s \in S} \omega_2(s\alpha x) \text{ where } [\alpha, x] \in R.$$

For a cubic set (L) $\mathcal{A}_3 = \langle \bar{\mu}_3, \omega_3 \rangle$ we define a cubic set (S) $\mathcal{A}_3^+ = \langle \bar{\mu}_3^+, \omega_3^+ \rangle = \langle (\bar{\mu}_3)^+, (\omega_3)^+ \rangle$ by

$$(\bar{\mu}_3)^+(x) = \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \bar{\mu}_3([x, \gamma]) \text{ and } (\omega_3)^+(x) = \sup_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \omega_3([x, \gamma]) \text{ where } x \in S.$$

For a cubic set (S) $\mathcal{A}_4 = \langle \bar{\mu}_4, \omega_4 \rangle$ we define a cubic set (L) $\mathcal{A}_4^{+1} = \langle \bar{\mu}_4^+, \omega_4^+ \rangle = \langle (\bar{\mu}_4)^{+1}, (\omega_4)^{+1} \rangle$ by

$$(\bar{\mu}_4)^{+1}([x, \alpha]) = \inf_{s \in S} \bar{\mu}_4(x\alpha s) \text{ and } (\omega_4)^{+1}([x, \alpha]) = \sup_{s \in S} \omega_4(x\alpha s) \text{ where } [x, \alpha] \in L.$$

Theorem 3.8: Every cubic ideal of a po- Γ -semigroup is cubic bi-ideal of a po- Γ -semigroup.

Proof: Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup and $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic ideal of S .

For any $x, y \in S$ with $x \leq y, \bar{\mu}(x) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x) \leq \omega(y)$

case(i) Suppose $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic left ideal of a po- Γ -semigroup S

$\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y) \geq \bar{\mu}(y), \omega(x\alpha y) \leq \omega(y)$ for all $x, y \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

For any $x, y, z \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$, we have

$$\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) = \bar{\mu}(x\alpha(y\beta z)) \geq \bar{\mu}(y\beta z) \geq \bar{\mu}(z) \text{ and}$$

$$\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) = \omega(x\alpha(y\beta z)) \leq \omega(y\beta z) \leq \omega(z)$$

case(ii) suppose $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic right ideal of a po- Γ -semigroup S

$\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y) \geq \bar{\mu}(x), \omega(x\alpha y) \leq \omega(x)$ for all $x, y \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

For any $x, y, z \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$, we have

$$\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) = \bar{\mu}((x\alpha y)\beta z) \geq \bar{\mu}(x\alpha y) \geq \bar{\mu}(x) \text{ and}$$

$$\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) = \omega((x\alpha y)\beta z) \leq \omega(x\alpha y) \leq \omega(x)$$

From the above two cases, we have

$$\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y) \geq \bar{\mu}(x) \wedge \bar{\mu}(y) = \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} \text{ and}$$

$$\omega(x\alpha y) \leq \omega(x) \vee \omega(y) = \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$$

Again, $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \bar{\mu}(x) \wedge \bar{\mu}(z) = \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\}$ and

$$\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \omega(x) \vee \omega(z) = \max\{\omega(x), \omega(z)\}$$

Hence $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S .

Theorem 3.9: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a non-empty cubic subsets of a po- Γ -semigroup S and

$\chi_{\mathcal{A}} = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}, \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}} \rangle$ be the characteristic cubic set of \mathcal{A} . Then \mathcal{A} is a left ideal (resp. right ideal, ideal) of S

if and only if the characteristic cubic set $\chi_{\mathcal{A}} = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}, \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}} \rangle$ of \mathcal{A} in S is a cubic left ideal

(resp. right ideal, ideal) of S.

Proof: Let \mathcal{A} be a non-empty cubic subsets of S and \mathcal{A} be a left ideal of S.

Let $x, y \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Then $x\alpha y \in \mathcal{A}$.

If $y \in \mathcal{A}$, it follows that $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y) = \bar{1} \geq \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y) = 0 \leq \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$

If $y \notin \mathcal{A}$, it follows that $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y) = \bar{0} \geq \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y) = 1 \leq \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$

Again, let $x, y \in S$ be such that $x \leq y$, if $y \in \mathcal{A}$ then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = \bar{1}$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = 0$

Since $x \leq y \in \mathcal{A}$, we have $x \in \mathcal{A}$, then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) = \bar{1}$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) = 0$

Hence $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) \geq \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) \leq \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$.

If $y \notin \mathcal{A}$, then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = \bar{0}$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = 1$

Hence we have $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) \geq \bar{0} = \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) \leq 1 = \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$

Therefore $\chi_{\mathcal{A}} = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}, \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}} \rangle$ is a cubic left ideal of S.

Conversly, let $\chi_{\mathcal{A}} = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}, \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}} \rangle$ be the cubic left ideal of S, let $x, y \in S$ and $y \in \mathcal{A}$.

Then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = \bar{1}$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = 0$. Since $\chi_{\mathcal{A}}$ is a cubic left ideal of S, then

$\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y) \geq \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y) \leq \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$.

So, $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y) = \bar{1}$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y) = 0$, then $x\alpha y \in \mathcal{A}$.

Now, if $x \leq y$ and $y \in \mathcal{A}$, then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = \bar{1}$, $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = 0$ and

$\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) \geq \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$, $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) \leq \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$

So, $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) = \bar{1}$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) = 0$, then $x \in \mathcal{A}$.

Thus $x \leq y$ and $y \in \mathcal{A}$, then $x \in \mathcal{A}$.

Therefore $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is left ideal of S.

Theorem 3.10: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a non-empty cubic subsets of a po- Γ -semigroup S and

$\chi_{\mathcal{A}} = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}, \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}} \rangle$ be the characteristic cubic set of \mathcal{A} . Then \mathcal{A} is an interior ideal of S

if and only if the characteristic cubic set $\chi_{\mathcal{A}} = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}, \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}} \rangle$ of \mathcal{A} in S is a cubic interior ideal of S.

Theorem 3.11: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a non-empty cubic subsets of a po- Γ -semigroup S and

$\chi_{\mathcal{A}} = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}, \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}} \rangle$ be the characteristic cubic set of \mathcal{A} . Then \mathcal{A} is a bi-ideal of S

if and only if the characteristic cubic set $\chi_{\mathcal{A}} = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}, \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}} \rangle$ of \mathcal{A} in S is a cubic bi-ideal of S.

Proof: Let \mathcal{A} be a non-empty subset of a po- Γ -semigroup S and \mathcal{A} be a bi-ideal of S.

Let $x, y, z \in S$. Then $xyz \in \mathcal{A}$, if $x, z \in \mathcal{A}$ and $x\alpha y\beta z \in \mathcal{A}$, if $x, y, z \in \mathcal{A}$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

It follows that $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y\beta z) = \bar{1} = \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x), \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(z)\}$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y\beta z) = 0 = \max\{\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x), \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(z)\}$

Let $x \notin \mathcal{A}$ or $z \notin \mathcal{A}$. Then,

case(i) If $x\alpha y\beta z \notin \mathcal{A}$, then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \bar{0} = \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x), \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(z)\}$ and

$$\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq 1 = \max\{\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x), \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(z)\}$$

case(ii) If $x\alpha y\beta z \in \mathcal{A}$, then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \bar{1} = \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x), \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(z)\}$ and

$$\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq 0 = \max\{\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x), \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(z)\}$$

Again, let $x, y \in S$ be such that $x \leq y$.

If $y \in \mathcal{A}$, then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = \bar{1}$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = 0$.

Since $x \leq y \in \mathcal{A}$, we have $x \in \mathcal{A}$, then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) = \bar{1}$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) = 0$

Thus $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) \geq \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) \leq \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$

Hence $\chi_{\mathcal{A}} = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}, \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}} \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S.

Conversly, let $\chi_{\mathcal{A}}$ be the cubic bi-ideal of S.

Let $x, y, z \in S$ be such that $x, z \in \mathcal{A}$ then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) = \bar{1} = \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(z)$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) = 0 = \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(z)$.

Also, $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x), \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(z)\} = \bar{1}$ and

$$\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \max\{\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x), \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(z)\} = 0.$$

Hence $x\alpha y\beta z \in \mathcal{A}$.

Again, let $x \in \mathcal{A}$ and $x \leq y$. Then we have $y \in \mathcal{A}$.

This implies that $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = \bar{1}$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = 0$.

Since $\chi_{\mathcal{A}}$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S, then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) = \bar{1} \geq \bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(x) = 0 \leq \omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y)$

Since $y \in S$, we have $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) \geq \bar{1}$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) \leq 0$.

Hence $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = \bar{1}$ and $\omega_{\chi_{\mathcal{A}}}(y) = 0$. So, $y \in \mathcal{A}$.

Consequently, \mathcal{A} is a bi-ideal of S.

Theorem 3.12: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic left (right) ideal of a po- Γ -semigroup S. Then so is

$\mathcal{A}^\alpha = \langle (\bar{\mu})^\alpha, (\omega)^\alpha \rangle$ for every real number $\alpha \geq 0$, where \mathcal{A}^α defined by $\mathcal{A}^\alpha(x) = (\mathcal{A}(x))^\alpha$ for all $x \in S$.

Proof: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic left ideal of a po- Γ -semigroup S. For any $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$.

We have $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x\alpha y) \leq \omega(y)$

Now $(\bar{\mu})^\alpha(x\alpha y) = (\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y))^\alpha \geq (\bar{\mu}(y))^\alpha = (\bar{\mu})^\alpha(y)$ and

$$(\omega)^\alpha(x\alpha y) = (\omega(x\alpha y))^\alpha \leq (\omega(y))^\alpha = (\omega)^\alpha(y).$$

Next, let $x, y \in S$, be such that $x \leq y$. Since \mathcal{A} is a cubic left ideal of S .

So, $\bar{\mu}(x) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x) \leq \omega(y)$ for all $x, y \in S$.

Then $(\bar{\mu}(x))^\alpha \geq (\bar{\mu}(y))^\alpha$ and $(\omega(x))^\alpha \leq (\omega(y))^\alpha$ for all $\alpha \geq 0$.

therefore $(\bar{\mu})^\alpha(x) \geq (\bar{\mu})^\alpha(y)$ and $(\omega)^\alpha(x) \leq (\omega)^\alpha(y)$

Hence $\mathcal{A}^\alpha = \langle (\bar{\mu})^\alpha, (\omega)^\alpha \rangle$ is a cubic left (right) ideal of S .

Theorem 3.13: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic interior ideal of a po- Γ -semigroup S . Then so is

$\mathcal{A}^\alpha = \langle (\bar{\mu})^\alpha, (\omega)^\alpha \rangle$ for every real number $\alpha \geq 0$, where \mathcal{A}^α defined by $\mathcal{A}^\alpha(x) = (\mathcal{A}(x))^\alpha$ for all $x \in S$.

Proof: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic interior ideal of a po- Γ -semigroup S . For any $x, y, z \in S$ and $\gamma, \beta \in \Gamma$.

We have $\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y\beta z) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x\gamma y\beta z) \leq \omega(y)$

Now $(\bar{\mu})^\alpha(x\gamma y\beta z) = (\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y\beta z))^\alpha \geq (\bar{\mu}(y))^\alpha = (\bar{\mu})^\alpha(y)$ and

$$(\omega)^\alpha(x\gamma y\beta z) = (\omega(x\gamma y\beta z))^\alpha \leq (\omega(y))^\alpha = (\omega)^\alpha(y).$$

Next, let $x, y \in S$, be such that $x \leq y$. Since \mathcal{A} is a cubic left ideal of S .

So, $\bar{\mu}(x) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x) \leq \omega(y)$ for all $x, y \in S$.

Then $(\bar{\mu}(x))^\alpha \geq (\bar{\mu}(y))^\alpha$ and $(\omega(x))^\alpha \leq (\omega(y))^\alpha$ for all $\alpha \geq 0$.

therefore $(\bar{\mu})^\alpha(x) \geq (\bar{\mu})^\alpha(y)$ and $(\omega)^\alpha(x) \leq (\omega)^\alpha(y)$

Hence $\mathcal{A}^\alpha = \langle (\bar{\mu})^\alpha, (\omega)^\alpha \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of S .

Proposition 3.14: Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup S and $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ be a non-empty family of cubic subsets of S .

Then $\Pi_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \langle \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i, \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i \rangle$ is a cubic subset of S .

Proof: Let $x \in S$. Then the set $\{\bar{\mu}_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ is non-empty bounded below subset of \mathbb{R} .

By the completeness axiom, there exist $\inf\{\bar{\mu}_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ in \mathbb{R} . Since $[0,0] \leq \bar{\mu}_i \leq [1,1]$ for each $i \in \Lambda$.

We have $[0,0] \leq \inf\{\bar{\mu}_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda} \leq [1,1]$. Thus $[0,0] \leq (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i)(x) \leq [1,1]$.

If $x, y \in S$, such that $x = y$, then $\{\bar{\mu}_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda} = \{\bar{\mu}_i(y)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$. Thus $\inf\{\bar{\mu}_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda} = \inf\{\bar{\mu}_i(y)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$.

So, $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(x) = \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(y)$.

Thus $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i$ is an interval-valued fuzzy subset of S .

And, the set $\{\omega_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ is non-empty bounded above subset of \mathbb{R} . By the completeness axiom, there exist $\sup\{\omega_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ in \mathbb{R} . Since $0 \leq \omega_i \leq 1$ for each $i \in \Lambda$, we have $0 \leq \sup\{\omega_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda} \leq 1$.

Thus $0 \leq \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(x) \leq 1$.

If $x, y \in S$ such that $x = y$ then $\{\omega_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda} = \{\omega_i(y)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$. Thus $\sup\{\omega_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda} = \sup\{\omega_i(y)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$.

This implies that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(x) = \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(y)$

Thus $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i$ is a fuzzy subset of S .

Hence $\Pi_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \langle \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i, \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i \rangle$ is a cubic subset of S .

Proposition 3.15: Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup and $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ be a family of cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S .

Then $\Pi_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \langle \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i, \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S .

Proof: By proposition (3.14) $\Pi_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a cubic subset of S .

Let $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ be the family of cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S , let $x, y, z \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Let $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(x) = \inf\{\bar{\mu}_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ and $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(x) = \sup\{\omega_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then } \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(x\alpha y) &= \inf\{\bar{\mu}_i(x\alpha y)\}_{i \in \Lambda} \geq \inf\{\min\{\bar{\mu}_i(x), \bar{\mu}_i(y)\}\}_{i \in \Lambda} = \min\{\inf\{\bar{\mu}_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda}, \inf\{\bar{\mu}_i(y)\}_{i \in \Lambda}\} \\ &= \min\{\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(x), \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(x\alpha y) &= \sup\{\omega_i(x\alpha y)\}_{i \in \Lambda} \geq \sup\{\max\{\omega_i(x), \omega_i(y)\}\}_{i \in \Lambda} = \max\{\sup\{\omega_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda}, \sup\{\omega_i(y)\}_{i \in \Lambda}\} \\ &= \max\{\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(x), \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\Pi_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \langle \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i, \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S .

Theorem 3.16: Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup and $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ be the family of cubic left (right) ideal of S . Then

$\Pi_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \langle \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i, \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i \rangle$ is a cubic left (right) ideal of S .

Proof: By proposition (3.14) $\Pi_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a cubic subset of S .

Now, let $x, y \in S$ be such that $x \leq y$.

Since $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ is the family of cubic left ideal of S then $\bar{\mu}_i(x) \geq \bar{\mu}_i(y)$ and $\omega_i(x) \leq \omega_i(y)$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

Thus $\inf\bar{\mu}_i(y) \leq \bar{\mu}_i(y) \leq \bar{\mu}_i(x)$ and $\sup\omega_i(y) \geq \omega_i(y) \geq \omega_i(x)$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

$\inf\{\bar{\mu}_i(y)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ is an lower bound of $\bar{\mu}_i(x)$ and $\sup\{\omega_i(y)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ is an upper bound of $\omega_i(x)$.

Hence $\inf\bar{\mu}_i(x) \geq \inf\bar{\mu}_i(y)$ and $\sup\omega_i(x) \leq \sup\omega_i(y)$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

So, $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(x) \geq \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(y)$ and $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(x) \leq \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(y)$.

Finally, let $x, y \in S$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Since $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ is the family of cubic left ideal of S .

We have $\bar{\mu}_i(x\alpha y) \geq \bar{\mu}_i(y)$ and $\omega_i(x\alpha y) \leq \omega_i(y)$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

$$\text{Thus } (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i)(x\alpha y) = (\inf\bar{\mu}_i)(x\alpha y)_{i \in \Lambda} = \inf\bar{\mu}_i(x\alpha y)_{i \in \Lambda} \geq \inf\bar{\mu}_i(y)_{i \in \Lambda} = \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(y).$$

$$\text{And } (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i)(x\alpha y) = (\sup\omega_i)(x\alpha y)_{i \in \Lambda} = \sup\omega_i(x\alpha y)_{i \in \Lambda} \leq \sup\omega_i(y)_{i \in \Lambda} = \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(y).$$

Hence $\Pi_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \langle \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i, \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i \rangle$ is a cubic left (right) ideal of S .

Theorem 3.17: Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup and $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ be the family of cubic bi-ideals of S . Then $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \langle \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i, \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S .

Proof: By proposition (3.15) we have $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S .

Now, let $x, y \in S$ be such that $x \leq y$. Since $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S , then $\bar{\mu}_i(x) \geq \bar{\mu}_i(y)$ and $\omega_i(x) \leq \omega_i(y)$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

Thus $\inf \bar{\mu}_i(y) \leq \bar{\mu}_i(y) \leq \bar{\mu}_i(x)$ and $\sup \omega_i(y) \geq \omega_i(y) \geq \omega_i(x)$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

$\inf \{\bar{\mu}_i(y)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ is an lower bound of $\bar{\mu}_i(x)$ and $\sup \{\omega_i(y)\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ is an upper bound of $\omega_i(x)$.

Hence $\inf \bar{\mu}_i(x) \geq \inf \bar{\mu}_i(y)$ and $\sup \omega_i(x) \leq \sup \omega_i(y)$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

So, $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(x) \geq \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(y)$ and $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(x) \leq \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(y)$.

Finally, let $x, y, z \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. Since $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ is the family of cubic bi-ideals of S , we have

$\bar{\mu}_i(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}_i(x), \bar{\mu}_i(z)\}$ and $\omega_i(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \max\{\omega_i(x), \omega_i(z)\}$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i)(x\alpha y\beta z) &= (\inf \bar{\mu}_i)(x\alpha y\beta z)_{i \in \Lambda} = \inf \bar{\mu}_i(x\alpha y\beta z)_{i \in \Lambda} \geq \inf \{\min\{\bar{\mu}_i(x), \bar{\mu}_i(z)\}\}_{i \in \Lambda} \\ &= \min\{\inf \{\bar{\mu}_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda}, \inf \{\bar{\mu}_i(z)\}_{i \in \Lambda}\} \end{aligned}$$

$$(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i)(x\alpha y\beta z) = \min\{\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(x), \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(z)\} \text{ and}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i)(x\alpha y\beta z) &= (\sup \omega_i)(x\alpha y\beta z)_{i \in \Lambda} = \sup \omega_i(x\alpha y\beta z)_{i \in \Lambda} \leq \sup \{\max\{\omega_i(x), \omega_i(z)\}\}_{i \in \Lambda} \\ &= \max\{\sup \{\omega_i(x)\}_{i \in \Lambda}, \sup \{\omega_i(z)\}_{i \in \Lambda}\} \end{aligned}$$

$$(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i)(x\alpha y\beta z) = \max\{\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(x), \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(z)\}$$

Hence $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \langle \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i, \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S .

Theorem 3.18: Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup and $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ be the family of cubic interior ideal of S . Then

$\prod_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \langle \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i, \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of S .

Proof: By proposition (3.15) we have $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S .

Now, let $x, y \in S$ be such that $x \leq y$. Since $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S , then $\bar{\mu}_i(x) \geq \bar{\mu}_i(y)$ and $\omega_i(x) \leq \omega_i(y)$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

Thus $\inf \bar{\mu}_i(y) \leq \bar{\mu}_i(y) \leq \bar{\mu}_i(x)$ and $\sup \omega_i(y) \geq \omega_i(y) \geq \omega_i(x)$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

And, let $x, y, z \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. Since $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ is the family of cubic interior ideals of S , we have

$\bar{\mu}_i(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \bar{\mu}_i(y)$ and $\omega_i(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \omega_i(y)$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

Thus $(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i)(x\alpha y\beta z) = (\inf \bar{\mu}_i)(x\alpha y\beta z)_{i \in \Lambda}$

$$= \inf \bar{\mu}_i(x\alpha y\beta z)_{i \in \Lambda}$$

$$\geq \inf \bar{\mu}_i(y)_{i \in \Lambda}$$

$$(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i)(x\alpha y\beta z) = \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i(y) \text{ and}$$

$$(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i)(x\alpha y\beta z) = (\sup \omega_i)(x\alpha y\beta z)_{i \in \Lambda}$$

$$= \sup \omega_i(x\alpha y\beta z)_{i \in \Lambda}$$

$$\leq \sup \omega_i(y)_{i \in \Lambda}$$

$$(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i)(x\alpha y\beta z) = \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i(y)$$

Hence $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \langle \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i, \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \omega_i \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of S .

Theorem 3.19: Let $f: S \rightarrow S^1$ be an epimorphism on po- Γ -semigroup S and S^1 . If $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -sub semigroup of S^1 by the cubic property then $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -sub semigroup of S , provided $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A})$ is non-empty.

Proof: Let $x, y \in S$. Then $C_f(x), C_f(y) \in S^1$. For any $\alpha \in \Gamma$ we have

since $\bar{\mu}$ is an interval-valued fuzzy Γ -sub semigroup of S^1

$$C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y)) = \bar{\mu}(f(x\alpha y))$$

$$= \bar{\mu}(f(x)\alpha f(y))$$

$$\geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(f(x)), \bar{\mu}(f(y))\}$$

$$C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y)) = \min\{C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x)), C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(y))\} \text{ and}$$

since ω is a fuzzy Γ -sub semigroup of S^1

$$C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\alpha y)) = \omega(f(x\alpha y))$$

$$= \omega(f(x)\alpha f(y))$$

$$\leq \max\{\omega(f(x)), \omega(f(y))\}$$

$$C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\alpha y)) = \max\{C_f^{-1}(\omega(x)), C_f^{-1}(\omega(y))\}$$

Hence $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -sub semigroup of S .

Theorem 3.20: Let $f: S \rightarrow S^1$ be an epimorphism on po- Γ -semigroup S and S^1 . If $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic left (right) ideal of S^1 by the cubic property then $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic left (right) ideal of S , provided $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A})$ is non-empty.

Proof: Let $x, y \in S$. Then $C_f(x), C_f(y) \in S^1$. For any $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Since $\bar{\mu}$ is an interval-valued fuzzy left ideal of S^1

$$C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y)) = \bar{\mu}(f(x\alpha y))$$

$$= \bar{\mu}(f(x)\alpha f(y))$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq \bar{\mu}(f(y)) \\ C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y)) &= C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(y)) \text{ and} \\ \text{since } \omega &\text{ is a fuzzy left ideal of } S^{-1} \\ C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\alpha y)) &= \omega(f(x\alpha y)) \\ &= \omega(f(x)\alpha f(y)) \\ &\leq \omega(f(y)) \end{aligned}$$

$C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\alpha y)) = C_f^{-1}(\omega(y))$
 Also, let $x, y \in S$ be such that $x \leq y$. Then $C_f(x), C_f(y) \in S^{-1}$ with $C_f(x) \leq C_f(y)$
 since $\bar{\mu}$ is an interval-valued fuzzy left ideal of S^{-1}
 so $\bar{\mu}(f(x)) \geq \bar{\mu}(f(y))$ then $C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x)) \geq C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(y))$ and
 since ω is a fuzzy left ideal of S^{-1}
 so $\omega(f(x)) \leq \omega(f(y))$ then $C_f^{-1}(\omega(x)) \leq C_f^{-1}(\omega(y))$
 Hence $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic left (right) ideal of S .

Theorem 3.21: Let $f: S \rightarrow S^{-1}$ be an epimorphism on po- Γ -semigroup S and S^{-1} . If $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S^{-1} by the cubic property then $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S , provided $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A})$ is non-empty.

Proof: By theorem (3.19) $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -sub semigroup of S .

Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S^{-1} and $x, y, z \in S$. Then $C_f(x), C_f(y), C_f(z) \in S^{-1}$. For any $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.
 since $\bar{\mu}$ is an interval-valued fuzzy bi-ideal of S^{-1}

$$\begin{aligned} C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z)) &= \bar{\mu}(f(x\alpha y\beta z)) \\ &= \bar{\mu}(f(x)\alpha f(y)\beta f(z)) \\ &\geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(f(x)), \bar{\mu}(f(z))\} \\ C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z)) &= \min\{C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x)), C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(z))\} \text{ and} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{since } \omega &\text{ is a fuzzy bi-ideal of } S^{-1} \\ C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\alpha y\beta z)) &= \omega(f(x\alpha y\beta z)) \\ &= \omega(f(x)\alpha f(y)\beta f(z)) \\ &\leq \max\{\omega(f(x)), \omega(f(z))\} \\ C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\alpha y\beta z)) &= \max\{C_f^{-1}(\omega(x)), C_f^{-1}(\omega(z))\} \end{aligned}$$

Also, let $x, y \in S$ be such that $x \leq y$. Then $C_f(x), C_f(y) \in S^{-1}$ with $C_f(x) \leq C_f(y)$
 since $\bar{\mu}$ is an interval-valued fuzzy bi-ideal of S^{-1}
 so $\bar{\mu}(f(x)) \geq \bar{\mu}(f(y))$ then $C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x)) \geq C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(y))$ and
 since ω is a fuzzy bi-ideal of S^{-1}
 so $\omega(f(x)) \leq \omega(f(y))$ then $C_f^{-1}(\omega(x)) \leq C_f^{-1}(\omega(y))$
 Hence $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S .

Theorem 3.22: Let $f: S \rightarrow S^{-1}$ be an epimorphism on po- Γ -semigroup S and S^{-1} . If $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of S^{-1} by the cubic property then $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of S , provided $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A})$ is non-empty.

Proof: By theorem (3.19) $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -sub semigroup of S .

Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic interior-ideal of S^{-1} and $x, y, z \in S$. Then $C_f(x), C_f(y), C_f(z) \in S^{-1}$.
 For any $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{since } \bar{\mu} &\text{ is an interval-valued fuzzy interior ideal of } S^{-1} \\ C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z)) &= \bar{\mu}(f(x\alpha y\beta z)) \\ &= \bar{\mu}(f(x)\alpha f(y)\beta f(z)) \\ &\geq \bar{\mu}(f(y)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z)) &= C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(y)) \text{ and} \\ \text{since } \omega &\text{ is a fuzzy interior ideal of } S^{-1} \\ C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\alpha y\beta z)) &= \omega(f(x\alpha y\beta z)) \\ &= \omega(f(x)\alpha f(y)\beta f(z)) \\ &\leq \omega(f(y)) \end{aligned}$$

$C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\alpha y\beta z)) = C_f^{-1}(\omega(y))$
 Also, let $x, y \in S$ be such that $x \leq y$. Then $C_f(x), C_f(y) \in S^{-1}$ with $C_f(x) \leq C_f(y)$
 since $\bar{\mu}$ is an interval-valued fuzzy interior ideal of S^{-1}
 so $\bar{\mu}(f(x)) \geq \bar{\mu}(f(y))$ then $C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x)) \geq C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(y))$ and
 since ω is a fuzzy interior ideal of S^{-1}
 so $\omega(f(x)) \leq \omega(f(y))$ then $C_f^{-1}(\omega(x)) \leq C_f^{-1}(\omega(y))$

Hence $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of S.

Proposition 3.23: Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup with unities, L be its left operator po-semigroup and $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic ideal of L (resp. cubic left ideal of L). Then $\mathcal{A}^+ = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle^+ = \langle (\bar{\mu})^+, \omega^+ \rangle$ is a cubic ideal of S (resp. cubic left ideal of S).

Proof: Let $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{\mu})^+(x\gamma y) &= \inf_{\alpha \in \Gamma} \bar{\mu}([x\gamma y, \alpha]) \\ &= \inf_{\alpha \in \Gamma} \bar{\mu}([x, \gamma][y, \alpha]) \\ &\geq \inf_{\alpha \in \Gamma} \bar{\mu}([y, \alpha]) \quad (\bar{\mu} \text{ is an CLI}(L)) \\ (\bar{\mu})^+(x\gamma y) &= (\bar{\mu})^+(y) \text{ and} \\ (\omega)^+(x\gamma y) &= \sup_{\alpha \in \Gamma} \omega([x\gamma y, \alpha]) \\ &= \sup_{\alpha \in \Gamma} \omega([x, \gamma][y, \alpha]) \\ &\leq \sup_{\alpha \in \Gamma} \omega([y, \alpha]) \quad (\omega \text{ is an CLI}(L)) \\ (\omega)^+(x\gamma y) &= (\omega)^+(y) \end{aligned}$$

Let $x, y \in S$ be such that $x \leq y$. Then $[x, \alpha] \leq [y, \alpha]$ in L for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Since $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a CI(L), then $\bar{\mu}[x, \alpha] \geq \bar{\mu}[y, \alpha]$ and $\omega[x, \alpha] \leq \omega[y, \alpha]$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{So, } (\bar{\mu})^+(x) &= \inf_{\alpha \in \Gamma} \bar{\mu}([x, \alpha]) \\ &\geq \inf_{\alpha \in \Gamma} \bar{\mu}([y, \alpha]) \\ (\bar{\mu})^+(x) &\geq (\bar{\mu})^+(y) \text{ and} \\ (\omega)^+(x) &= \sup_{\alpha \in \Gamma} \omega([x, \alpha]) \\ &\leq \sup_{\alpha \in \Gamma} \omega([y, \alpha]) \\ (\omega)^+(x) &\leq (\omega)^+(y) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mathcal{A}^+ = \langle (\bar{\mu})^+, \omega^+ \rangle$ is a cubic ideal of S.

Corollary 3.24: Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup with unities, R be its right operator po-semigroup and $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic ideal of R (resp. cubic left ideal of R). Then

$\mathcal{A}^* = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle^* = \langle (\bar{\mu})^*, \omega^* \rangle$ is a cubic ideal of S (resp. cubic left ideal of S).

Proposition 3.25: Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup with unities, L be its left operator po-semigroup and $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic ideal of S (resp. cubic left ideal of S). Then

$\mathcal{A}^{+1} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle^{+1} = \langle (\bar{\mu})^{+1}, \omega^{+1} \rangle$ is a cubic ideal of L (resp. cubic left ideal of L)

Proof: Let $[x, \alpha], [y, \beta] \in L$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{\mu})^{+1}([x, \alpha][y, \beta]) &= (\bar{\mu})^{+1}([x\alpha y, \beta]) \\ &= \inf_{s \in S} \bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta s) \\ &= \inf_{s \in S} \bar{\mu}(x\alpha(y\beta s)) \\ &\geq \inf_{s \in S} \bar{\mu}(y\beta s) \quad (\bar{\mu} \text{ is an CLI}(S)) \\ (\bar{\mu})^{+1}([x, \alpha][y, \beta]) &= (\bar{\mu})^{+1}([y, \beta]) \text{ and} \\ (\omega)^{+1}([x, \alpha][y, \beta]) &= (\omega)^{+1}([x\alpha y, \beta]) \\ &= \sup_{s \in S} \omega(x\alpha y\beta s) \\ &= \sup_{s \in S} \omega(x\alpha(y\beta s)) \\ &\leq \sup_{s \in S} \omega(y\beta s) \quad (\omega \text{ is an CLI}(S)) \end{aligned}$$

$$(\omega)^{+1}([x, \alpha][y, \beta]) = (\omega)^{+1}([y, \beta])$$

Now, let $[x, \alpha], [y, \alpha] \in L$ be such that $[x, \alpha] \leq [y, \alpha]$. Then $x\alpha s \leq y\alpha s$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$ and $s \in S$.

Since $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a CI(S), then $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha s) \geq \bar{\mu}(y\alpha s)$ and $\omega(x\alpha s) \leq \omega(y\alpha s)$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$ and $s \in S$.

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{\mu})^{+1}([x, \alpha]) &= \inf_{s \in S} \bar{\mu}(x\alpha s) \\ &\geq \inf_{s \in S} \bar{\mu}(y\alpha s) \end{aligned}$$

$$(\bar{\mu})^{+1}([x, \alpha]) \geq (\bar{\mu})^{+1}([y, \alpha]) \text{ and}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\omega)^{+1}([x, \alpha]) &= \sup_{s \in S} \omega(x\alpha s) \\ &\leq \sup_{s \in S} \omega(y\alpha s) \end{aligned}$$

$$(\omega)^{+1}([x, \alpha]) \leq (\omega)^{+1}([y, \alpha])$$

Hence $\mathcal{A}^{+1} = \langle (\bar{\mu})^{+1}, \omega^{+1} \rangle$ is a cubic ideal of L.

Corollary 3.26: Let S be a po- Γ -semigroup with unities, R be its right operator po-semigroup and $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic ideal of S (resp. cubic left ideal of S). Then

$\mathcal{A}^{*1} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle^{*1} = \langle (\bar{\mu})^{*1}, \omega^{*1} \rangle$ is a cubic ideal of R (resp. cubic left ideal of R).

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